

IMPACT OF CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT ON CLINICAL PRACTICE: A QUALITATIVE STUDY

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Abstract

Background: Improving nurses' clinical practice and patient care depends on Continuing Professional Development (CPD), which provides healthcare professionals with current knowledge and skills.

Objective: The aim is to evaluate the influence of CPD on clinical practice among registered nurses, including the perceived benefits, barriers, and facilitators encountered during their professional development.

Materials & Methods: The study was conducted in General Hospital and Mental Hospital, Lahore, from June to November 2024, the study utilized a convenience sampling technique to select a sample of 20 registered nurses actively working in these hospitals. An interview guide was used to gather demographic data and insights related to participation in CPD, its impact on practice, and encountered challenges. Ethical considerations, including informed consent and confidentiality, were maintained throughout the research process. Data was analyzed using NVivo software to draw conclusions based on thematic analysis of the qualitative data collected.

Results: The results indicated that Continuing Professional Development (CPD) has a significant impact on nurses' clinical practices, career advancement, and patient care results. Respondents highlighted the importance of CPD in keeping abreast of the latest developments in healthcare through workshops, virtual courses, and collaborative learning experiences. Notable outcomes included boost in knowledge, increased confidence, and improved recovery rates for patients. Nevertheless, common challenges such as limited resources, staffing concerns, and insufficient organizational support were often mentioned. Participants proposed solutions like expanding online CPD options, better resource management, enhanced leadership backing, and fostering peer encouragement to overcome these challenges, emphasizing CPD's vital role in promoting nursing practice.

Conclusion: The findings from this study will offer valuable insights into the significance of CPD in nursing practice, emphasizing the need for improved support and resources to enhance professional development.

INTRODUCTION

Continuing Professional Development (CPD) is essential in clinical practice as it enables healthcare professionals, particularly nurses, to continually update their knowledge, skills, and competencies in response to evolving healthcare

needs (Athyaha Hanaif Alruwaily et al., 2022). CPD ensures safe, evidence-based, and effective patient care while enhancing professional competence and motivation (Nuelisani et al., 2023). Structured programs such as workshops, conferences, e-learning, and practical training

provide opportunities for lifelong learning, allowing nurses to stay current with advances in technology, treatment protocols, and patient care standards (Nanayakkara et al., 2023).

Research highlights that CPD positively impacts healthcare outcomes by improving patient safety, enhancing clinical performance, and fostering teamwork among healthcare providers (Manley et al., 2018). Active participation in CPD equips nurses to respond effectively to public health challenges, adopt evidence-based practices, and reflect critically on their performance (Amir et al., 2024). Furthermore, CPD contributes to professional growth, job satisfaction, and reduced burnout, ultimately creating a more skilled and motivated nursing workforce (Mlambo et al., 2021).

Despite its recognized benefits, CPD implementation faces barriers such as time limitations, financial constraints, and lack of institutional support (Samuel et al., 2021). Overcoming these challenges requires well-structured, accessible, and outcome-focused CPD programs, including digital and inter-professional learning approaches (Garey, 2022). By strengthening CPD initiatives, healthcare organizations can promote a culture of continuous improvement, ensuring that practitioners remain competent, confident, and patient-centered. Ultimately, effective CPD

benefits not only professionals but also patients and healthcare systems as a whole (Vázquez-Calatayud et al., 2021)

Can you describe a situation where CPD led to enhanced patient outcomes?

Methodology

A qualitative study was conducted at General Hospital and Mental Hospital, Lahore, from June 2024 to November 2024. A total of 20 registered female nurses with more than five years of professional experience were selected through convenience sampling to explore the impact of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) on clinical practice, while male nurses, students, and those unwilling or unavailable were excluded. Data were collected through in-depth interviews using a structured interview guide that covered demographic information, participation, impact, barriers, facilitation, and experiences. Ethical approval was obtained from the concerned institutional authority, and informed consent was taken from participants with assurances of confidentiality, privacy, voluntary participation, and protection from harm. Data from interviews were recorded, stored securely, and analyzed using NVivo software to identify recurring themes and draw meaningful conclusions.

Results

Table 1: Table showing the participants demographic data

Participant	Sex	Educational Level	Work Role	Work Experience
P1	Female	MSc	Head Nurse	5
P2	Female	MSc	Head Nurse	5+
P3	Female	BSc	Charge Nurse	5+
P4	Female	MSc	Head Nurse	5+
P5	Female	BSc	Charge Nurse	5+
P6	Female	BSc	Charge Nurse	5+

Table 1 presents the demographic information of the study participants. All ten participants were female nurses, with educational qualifications ranging from BSc to MSc in nursing. Their work roles included charge nurses and head nurses, with all having more than five years of professional experience

P7	Female	BSc	Charge Nurse	5 +
P8	Female	BSc	Charge Nurse	5+
P9	Female	BSc	Charge Nurse	5 +
P10	Female	BSc	Charge Nurse	5+

What types of CPD have you participated in (e.g. workshops, conferences,online courses)?

Table 2: Table showing interview guide

Interview Guide
Section I-Participation
How do you currently stay up-to-date with the latest developments and advancements in your field?
How often do you participate in CPD activities?
Section II-Impact
How do you think CPD has impacted your clinical practice? Can you give an example of a specific CPD activity that changed your practice?
Section III-Challenges
What challenges or barriers have you faced in implementing CPD into your clinical practice? How do you overcome these challenges?
Section IV-Implementation
How do you use what you learn from training and education in your daily clinical work? Can you describe any help you get from your workplace to use what you've learned?
Section V-Suggestions
How do you use what you learn from training and education in your daily clinical work? Can you describe any help you get from your workplace to use what you've learned?

The interview guide consisted of five parts: Participation, which delved into how nurses remained informed and involved in CPD activities; Impact, which centered on the effect of CPD on clinical practice and patient outcomes; Challenges, which dealt with obstacles to CPD implementation; Implementation, which examined the real-world application of acquired skills; and Suggestions, which aimed to gather input on workplace support and enhancements for incorporating CPD into daily practice.

Themes	Categories	Sub-Categories
Staying up-to date with latest technology	Formal Education and training	Attend regular workshop,Conferences,Seminars,Training,Webinars,Workshops
	Online and Self-learning	Join discussions in clinical forums, Online courses,Reading research articles, Reading Journals,Social media,Subscription services for medical platforms
	Collaborative Learning	Case studies discussion,Educational activities
Example of CPD usage	Application of knowledge	Implementing knowledge,new practices CPD on basis on new techniques, practicing the theoretical knowledge
	Specific Practices	Handwashing techniques,hardworking activities
Outcomes	Knowledge and Learning	Improve knowledge, Learning and improvement within team Professional growth,Professional networking
	Professional Development Patient Outcome	Enhanced care,Patient communication,Improved patient condition,Patient fast recovery,Reduced patient infection and pain
Challenges	Resource Limitation	Financial constraint, Poor Budget, lack of resource or equipment
	Staffing issue	Availability of the staff,Unskilled available staff

	Lack of Support	Lack of support from organization or seniors
	Time Management	Lack of time,workload
Suggestion	Educational and technical enhancement	Online Classes,technology enhancement
	Efficient Resources	Utilize available resources, Management of the resources
	Leadership and Support	Counselling about CPD,Convincing the seniors or management of organization
	Personal and peer motivation	Motivation

Theme 1: Staying up-to-date with Latest Technology

The theme focuses on how nurses consistently strive to stay up to date with the latest developments in healthcare technologies, tools, and methods. Data indicates that nurses use a combination of formal education, self-directed online learning, and collaborative learning to ensure that their knowledge and skills are current. Nurses highlighted the significance of participating in regular workshops, conferences, seminars, training sessions, and webinars. These formal educational activities are seen as essential for keeping healthcare professionals informed about the rapidly changing medical technologies. As one participant mentioned:

"I make it a point to attend every tech workshop and conference I can. It keeps me aligned with the latest practices, especially in terms of patient care."

Nevertheless, there were certain obstacles related to accessing these opportunities. A few attendees encountered problems in obtaining time off from their jobs, while others highlighted the financial strain of participating in expensive workshops and seminars.

Participants utilized online platforms and self-learning techniques to keep themselves informed. Common approaches included participating in clinical forums, signing up for online courses, perusing research articles, and subscribing to medical education platforms.

The accessibility of these platforms enabled nurses to engage with learning resources at their own convenience. One participant shared:

"Online courses and forums are a lifesaver when I can't attend workshops in person. I can still stay informed without disrupting my work schedule."

Some nurses believed that the use of online platforms limited chances for practical training, which they viewed as essential for gaining skills. Nurses often participated in educational activities

and engaged in case study discussions within their teams, emphasizing the significance of collaborative learning. Peers were able to exchange knowledge and skills through this collaborative approach. A participant noted:
"Discussing real-life case studies with colleagues helps me apply what I learn in a more practical way. It's like putting theory into practice immediately."

Theme 2: Example of CPD Usage

The focus of this topic is on how nurses implement recently gained knowledge into their everyday work, emphasizing the practical use of continuing professional development (CPD) in nursing practice. After engaging in CPD activities, participants shared the different methods they used to apply the knowledge acquired, especially the new practices and techniques introduced during these sessions. It was common for them to mention integrating new techniques into their daily routines as a way of putting theoretical knowledge into practice. One nurse shared:

"I applied the knowledge from a recent CPD course on ventilator management, and it drastically improved how I care for ICU patients."

The influence of CPD was often cited in relation to specific practices like handwashing methods and strenuous activities. Nurses emphasized the importance of these practices in maintaining patient safety and minimizing infections. As one participant reflected:

"The handwashing technique we learned in CPD has become second nature, and it's significantly reduced infection rates in our unit."

Theme 3: Outcomes

The theme delves into the results that nurses encounter following their involvement in CPD initiatives, which are classified into knowledge acquisition and learning, career advancement, and patient results. The participants noted a

notable enhancement in their understanding, especially in dealing with intricate cases and acquiring knowledge as part of a team. One nurse stated:

"CPD has improved my ability to work with my team in managing challenging patient cases. I feel more knowledgeable and confident in my decisions."

Professional development (CPD) was considered a key element in the advancement of one's career and building professional relationships. Nurses appreciated the chance to engage with fellow professionals and enhance their abilities. A participant shared: *"Through CPD, I've grown professionally. It's not just about learning new techniques but also about building a network of colleagues who can support me in my practice."*

The theme of improved patient outcomes was frequently mentioned by nurses, who observed better care, improved communication with patients, and quicker recoveries. Those taking part in the program associated CPD with a decrease in patient infections and pain, crediting this to their use of current practices. One participant remarked: *"Thanks to the CPD training on infection control, our patients are recovering faster, and we've seen a significant drop in post-surgical infections."*

Theme 4: Challenges

Obstacles associated with CPD involvement were grouped into constraints on resources, staffing challenges, insufficient support, and difficulties with time management. Nurses highlighted a significant hurdle, citing inadequate financial resources and equipment required to actively participate in CPD. Common grievances included restricted budgets and obsolete resources, as one participant expressed:

"We have the knowledge, but without the proper resources or budget, we can't apply what we've learned effectively."

Nurses identified a shortage of staff as a challenge in participating in CPD. It was hard to find qualified staff to cover shifts, making it challenging to attend training without impacting patient care. As one nurse explained:

"It's hard to attend CPD courses when the ward is already understaffed. There's simply no one to cover for me."

Some individuals faced challenges with obtaining support from their organization or senior management when engaging in CPD activities,

which ultimately impeded their efforts to stay current. One participant commented:

"Convincing the management to support CPD is a constant struggle. They don't always see the immediate benefit, but it's essential for improving patient care."

Frequently, nurses mentioned struggling to balance their workload with CPD activities due to time constraints. One participant shared:

"With our workload, it's hard to find the time for CPD, even though we know it's crucial for our development."

Theme 5: Suggestions

Suggestions were provided by participants to enhance the accessibility and effectiveness of CPD, which were grouped into educational improvement, effective management of resources, support for leadership, and motivation. Numerous nurses recommended the expansion of online courses and the incorporation of contemporary technologies into CPD programs to enhance accessibility. One participant shared:

"We need more online options and advanced technologies to make CPD easier to access, especially for those of us in remote areas."

The importance of maximizing existing resources and efficiently handling them to aid CPD was highlighted by participants. One nurse stated:

"The hospital needs to better manage the resources we already have and ensure they're available for use in CPD training."

Nurses have requested increased support from their leaders, especially in providing guidance on the significance of CPD and persuading senior staff to allocate resources for these endeavors.

One participant explained:

"Our leaders need to be more proactive in supporting CPD. Convincing them is often the hardest part."

The significance of personal drive and support from peers in pursuing CPD was also brought up by participants. A participant highlighted:

"Staying motivated and encouraging colleagues to do the same is key. We push each other to attend CPD events and improve ourselves."

Conclusion

In summary, this research emphasizes the significant influence of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) on the clinical skills, decision-making confidence, and overall professional development of nurses. The results highlight the importance of CPD as a crucial aspect of nursing practice, demonstrating that the

majority of participants saw considerable enhancements in their capabilities and career advancement through their participation in CPD activities. Nevertheless, obstacles such as heavy workloads, time constraints, and financial constraints were recognized, emphasizing the necessity for increased employer assistance and flexible scheduling to facilitate participation. The study also underscores the importance of hands-on training and regular updates on healthcare advancements as essential components for effective CPD. Overall, the knowledge gained from this study can guide the creation of more accessible and impactful CPD programs, ultimately contributing to improved patient care and outcomes within the nursing profession. Wong et al. (2021); Falguera et al. (2020) & Hariyati et al (2018)

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